

INTER-STATE TRADE IN DONKEY MEAT: SOKOTO AND SOUTH-EASTERN NIGERIA IN THE 21ST CENTURY

By

Abubakar Tukur Muhammad
History Department,
Sokoto State University, Sokoto
abubakartukur3@gmail.com
07060581139

&

Murtala Marafa
Department of History,
Sokoto State University, Sokoto
marafamurtala02@gmail.com

Abstract

Donkey trade in the past was carried out by people within their localities, which made them very central in the conduct of the trade. In fact, in the early period, the trade was entirely neglected and there were few people that had a stake in the trade. The prices were very low, so also the profit. This was what made the entire trade a localized one. However, with time donkey trade became a lucrative trade, this is largely because of the recent changes in the pattern of the trade. The Consumption of Donkey meat by the Igbo people in the east further changed the pattern of trade which also brought about major development in the trade both in southern Nigeria and in Sokoto State. Donkey meat turned out to be an important meat for many people in the south eastern parts of Nigeria where the meat is being consumed due to its lower price compared to other livestock. The trade also attracted different people from different background thus the price of donkey has risen which further increased the profit and wealth creation of the traders. The paper studies the development of donkey trade between southern Nigeria and the people of Sokoto State. In the final analysis the paper analyses the development of the trade due the consumption of donkey meat.

Keywords: Meat, Consumption, Southerners, Slaughter, Trade, Market, Selling.

1.0 Introduction

The primary function of donkey in Nigeria and indeed all over the World

has been that of beast of burden. Initially it was used to carry loads from one place to another. But, later on the trade has

changed from that of load carrying to that of consumption of its meat by the people in the south east.¹

The development of donkey meat market in Nigeria could be traced back to the early 1970s when southern people began to come to northern parts of the country to buy donkeys and transport them to their region to be slaughtered and sold to consumers. But there are many sources which indicated that consumption of donkey meat is an old tradition in south-eastern Nigeria. For instance, there is renowned donkey meat market in Ezamgbo, Ebonyi state which has existed for over eighty (80) years and where about 200 donkeys are slaughtered in the market every day.² Southerners began to come to Sokoto to buy donkey and transfer them to their areas for human consumption around 1973. Later, a donkey slaughtering camp was established at illela town in Sokoto State. But this was closed owing to the religious and cultural tenets of the Sokoto people.³ The aim of paper of this paper is to study the development of donkey meat consumption and its thriving trade in Sokoto. Therefore, in order to achieve these objectives, the paper is divided into five (5) sections. Section one introduced the content of the paper. Section two; examined the nature and the risk involved in conveying donkeys to southern parts, while section

three (3) discussed the pattern of preparation of donkey meat and other issues related to it. Section four, provided an analysis on consumption of donkey meat and its impact on the trade. The last section is the conclusion of the paper.

2.0 Cost and Risk of Transportation

Drivers played very vital role in the movement of donkeys to southern Nigeria. A driver affirmed that he conveys donkeys to Danko/Rarah towns where donkeys are slaughtered and processed for selling to consumers. Donkey owners paid drivers between N20,000.00 and N35,000.00 for the transportation of a truck of donkey. The price is determined by the availability or other wise of carriage and market forces.⁴ The drivers play an important role in the trade; they are the one who convey donkeys to various places in the country. Donkeys are conveyed from Illela market to Danko/Rarah towns in Kebbi State for between N40,000.00 and N45,000.00. Owners of the animals encounter a lot of problems with the security personnel before they are able to convey donkeys to their places of business. It is alleged that they pay about 10,000.00 per truck at military check-points. There are also police check points which had no fixed price. They collect N10,000.00 or any amount they deemed

¹ <http://www.ccb.com>. Accessed 10/4/2015.

² <http://www.ccb.com>. Accessed 10/4/2015

³ Interview with, NahantsiSikeli, b.1932, Sokoto Kara Market, Sokoto, 16/12/2016

⁴ Interview with, Ibrahim Abubakar Mahuta, Driver of Lorry, 30 Years, Illela Market, 29/10/2016.

fit⁵. A driver conveys donkey meat with lorry from Danko town in Zuru Local Government area to Ibadan or Onitsha (Anambra State) at the rate of N110,000 and N120,000.00. He also conveys donkey skin from Danko town to Badagry Lagos at the rate of N130,000.00 and N140,000.00.⁶ Drivers who convey donkeys to southern parts are reportedly scarred due to the risk involved in the transportation. There is also rising cost of fuel that could lead to reduction in the expected profit of the driver. In the past, drivers charged between N250,000.00 and 450,000.00 to transport donkeys from Sokoto State to Ezamgbo in Ebonyi State and Agbor in Delta State, all in the southern part of the country.⁷

An informant confirmed that money charge by the drivers for transportation is not fixed. According to him, as at first week of November, 2015 N260,000.00 was paid to drivers and later the price increased to N320,000.00 during the second week of November, 2015. Besides, there is every tendency of price change as the price is determined by the season and availability of vehicles.⁸ Loaders and off-loaders were paid N12,000.00 for loading between donkeys

into a trailer while off-loaders are given N2,000.00 for the loaded donkeys from a trailer.⁹ The transportation of donkeys had no specific price and vehicle are sometimes scarce so that donkeys bought especially by the southerners could take a long time before they are evacuated to respective destinations. Also there are some traders who are behind the scarcity of vehicles and their expensive nature. Such groups of people are wealthy enough to pay the vehicle at any cost and most time traders negotiate with “Yan kwamisho” (Road Transport Workers) to get them vehicles. Sometimes, they have to bribe them with money amounting to N10,000.00 or N15,000.00 or more. Thereby contributing to the high cost of vehicles which traders are forced to pay. Those who could not afford to pay such higher prices would not get the vehicle on time¹⁰.

A donkey is normally loaded into a vehicle for between N80 and N100.00. The difference in the price is a function of the number of donkeys. Donkey also could be loaded at the rate of N100.00 if the donkeys to be loaded are few. Loaders usually arrange loading of

⁵ Interview with Abubabar Sani, 32 years, Lorry Driver, Illela Market, 29/10/2016

⁶ Interview with Yusuf Umar, 40 Years, Driver Illela Market, 5/11/2016

⁷ Interview with Na Allah Umaru, 40 years, Driver Illela Market 5/11/2016

⁸ Interview with, Emek Lekadi, 40 Years, Donkey Trader, Sokoto Kara Market, 11/11/2016

⁹ Interview with Emeka Lekadi... The difference in the money paid to them was that, loading was much difficult because they had to use rope and tie the animals and later lift them up into a vehicle and there was risk of being injured by the donkey, while it was easier than off-loading since donkeys were already in the vehicle people would only push them down from the vehicle

¹⁰ Interview with Emeka Lekadi ... I paid visit to Head Office of Donkeys and Horses Traders Association, Sokoto

donkeys in trailers that can contain 60 – 80 donkeys at the rate of N8,000.00 – N10,000.00. Lorries are also loaded with donkeys for between N3,000.00 and N4,000.00 respectively.¹¹ According to an informant, there is existing Donkey Loaders Association headed by the “Sarkin Lodi” and a lucky loader could get between N3,000.00 and N4,000.00 or more weekly.¹² The development of the trade has led to the emergence of many job opportunities among various groups. The transportation of donkeys to various places especially to southern parts of the country is profitable since a driver can make huge amount of money.¹³ For example, a trailer that conveys donkeys to the southern parts could be paid an amount ranging from N250,000 to N300,000.00 or more because it depended on the time and the condition of fuel availability or otherwise in the country.¹⁴ Another informant also described donkey trade as lucrative since people could make money from it. The trade is however, associated with risks including the fact that the animals could easily die to the delay in conveying them to their destination caused mostly by breakdown of the vehicles on the road, extortion of money by the security personnel especially police who had no fixed or specific amount that they

charged. For instance, they could charge N2,000.00, N5,000.00, N10,000.00 and up to N25,000.00 but soldiers had their own fixed fee of N2,000.00 per checking point or otherwise.¹⁵ The trends in donkey trade had been described as profitable, for even though the animal had no fixed price, people could make as much profit as N200,000.00 and N300,000.00 per trailer conveying 91 - 92 donkeys.¹⁶

3.0 Trade In Donkey Meat

The booming of donkey trade got so profitable that several donkey slaughter camps were established in many places in Nigeria. Such slaughter camps were established close to where the donkeys were sold. Some people bought donkeys and took them to other place while some slaughter the animals and roast their meat for onward transportation to places where the meat is patronized. In Mararrabah Idah donkey market, the meat is not sold but the traders slaughter the animals and roast their meat which they take to Zuba (near Abuja) for transportation to the southern parts of the country.¹⁷ Every part of the animal is sold from the head, skin and bones, all are marketable. The bones are sold after they had been burnt to ashes.¹⁸ The tail of the animal is not sold separately but

¹¹ Nura Umar, Loader, Oal interview, 53 Years, Driver, Sokoto New Motor Park 10/5/2016

¹² Interview with Nura Umar

¹³ Interview with Namadina Yusuf, Oral interview, 53 years, driver, Sokoto New Motor Park 10/5/2016

¹⁴ Interview with Namadina Yufu

¹⁵ Interview with, innocent Isioma

¹⁶ Interview with, innocent Isioma

¹⁷ Interview with, Alh Abdulazizu Mamman

¹⁸ Interview with, Alh Abdulazizu Mamman.. The development of donkey trade has presently divided the traders into groups.

attached to the hide because the tail had not much meat like that of a cow. At Agbor donkey market, about 150 – 200 donkeys are slaughtered and sometimes about 400 donkeys could be slaughtered in a day. A trader will spend about N3,000.00 to slaughter and sell fresh donkey meat to buyers. This is made up of the money for slaughtering, butchering, softening the skin, washing the intestines etc. A trader could spend about and seven trailers could be loaded with donkeys for onward conveyance to the Agbor Market every day.¹⁹

The development of donkey trade is a lucrative business for many people who work in Agbor donkey market. Every week, people come from different places to buy donkey meat such as Imo, Anambra, Bayelsa, Cross-River, Ekiti, etc.²⁰ Donkey remained an important animal where it was traded in the Eastern region even before the Civil War of 1967 – 1970. Trade in donkey meat flourished after the war in Eha Amufu in Northeastern Anambra State and many other areas in southern parts of Nigeria.²¹ In Madam Jaki slaughter camp, about twenty (20) donkeys are slaughtered

daily, depending on demand within Agbor town and nearby villages.²² Madam *Jaki* as she is popularly called is a renowned donkey meat seller in Agbor. The woman spent over 25 years in the business. She sale both fresh and fried donkey meat. A big chunk of the meat is sold at N50 and small piece of the meat at N 25. The least price of fresh donkey meat sold in her shop is N300.00. Donkeys are relatively cheaper than cows and this is one of the reasons why some people prefer donkey meat.²³ People sale its oil at the rate of N6000.00 per 40 liters which is used n frying chicken, beef and soup makings across different parts of southern Nigeria.

Furthermore, donkey skins sold at Marrabah Idah at the rate of N45,000.00 – N 50,000.00 (depending on the size), while the small size sales between N38,000 and N40,000 and the price of the skin is almost the same in Agbor, Ezamgbo and Dankomarkets. Besides, donkey bones are used in making tiles, breakable plates among other things. Bones are later burnt into ashes and packed in sacks. The price of one sack of such powdered bone is between N 35,000.00 – N40,000.00. This and other reason resulted in the hiking of the animal's price, since they earn their profit as soon as the animals reached

¹⁹ Interview with, Abdulazizu Mamman... information gathered that, such slaughtered donkey are fried and later took to other places for sale and there were some days where more than 200 donkeys could be slaughtered.

²⁰ Interview with, Emeka Agbor, 45 Years, Dealer of Donkey and Donkey Skin, Agbor, Delta State, 24/12/2016

²¹ P.O Okeinyeto et al, "Donkey Marketing in Producing and consuming states of Nigeria, in savanna journal Vol. 20.

²² <http://www.dailytrust.com.Booming> of Donkey Trade Accessed 1/12015

²³ Interview with, Madam jaki

their destinations.²⁴ Madam Esther confirmed that she buys 2 – 4 donkeys every day which meat she cooks/roast and sell to people. She sells a piece of the meat at N50 and six to seven small pieces at N 100.00. She added that she sells one sack of the bones after they were burnt at the rate of between N30,000.00 and N40,000.00.²⁵ Madam Favour who also sells donkey meat said she spends about N3,500.00 – N5,000.00 to process the meat for selling to consumers. She sells the least plate of donkey meat at the rate of N300,00 (which contains eight to ten pieces). She also sales the least plate of intestine at N250 which contain seven pieces of intestines.²⁶ Madam Chinyere buys donkeys, slaughters, fries and then packs in sacks and transport to Akure, ondo State for sale. She earns about N8,000.00 to N12,000.00 as profit per donkey.²⁷ The trade is lucrative and has attracted a lot of competition among the traders.²⁸ The trade is remarkable because it provides job opportunities to many people such as loaders who received N12,000 for loading donkeys in trailers, off-loaders also earn N2,000.00 for off-

loading donkeys from trailers. Women also buy donkeys and slaughter, process the meat and hawk it in markets. A big piece of roasted donkey meat was N50 and two small pieces are sold at N50. There are also some people who sell dried donkey meat to hotels and restaurants. Butchers who slaughter and butcher donkey could earn N1,000.00 per donkey; people who wash the intestine earned N200.00, while N150.00 is also given to those who break the bones into pieces. As well people who wash and soften the skin earn N200.00, while N 150,00.²⁹

4.0 Consumption of Donkey Meat and Its impact on the Trade

Donkey trade thrived in southern Nigerian markets; especially in the Igbo regions and the cross-river areas in Nigeria. The Trade is in smoked donkey meat, as donkeys bought are slaughtered and skinned while the meat is prepared through drying and smoking for consumption.³⁰ Donkey meat is the culinary term for the flesh of donkey which is served in many dishes. The consumption of donkey meat is common in Europe and China.³¹ Donkey burger is a sandwich popular in Chinese cusiness, which use the meat of donkey as the stuffing for the spicy and delicious sandwich. The meat is consumed in

²⁴ Interview with, Irughe Nice day... informant has opportune to visit

²⁵ Interview with Madam Esther

²⁶ Interview with Madam Favour, 45 years Donkey Meat Seller

²⁷ Interview with madam Chinyere, 40 years, Donkey Meat Seller

²⁸ Interview with, Alh. Sani Na Isa... informant affirmed that he used to encounter such difficulties most times when he sent donkeys to southern region and added that this was the most challenge facing the trade

²⁹ Interview with, Alh. Sani Na Isa

³⁰ Interview with Alh Basiru Sokoto, Donkey Trader, 50 Years, Ezamgbo Donkey Market, Enbonyi State 23/12/2016

³¹ <File://sys-18/users/public.retrived> 10/6/2016

many European and African countries and plays a vital role in uplifting the economic status of its traders in such countries.³²

Sources indicated that donkey traded for its meat started in former northwestern state (sokoto area) around 1974 by Igbo people attending some livestock markets such as Illela, Unguwar Makera, Dabon Birni, Goronyo, Bodinga, etc. in Sokoto State. They established a donkey slaughter camp in Gulbinka Forest in Daki Takwas (the present Zamfara State). They bought many donkeys up to 106 donkeys and 50 horses that were slaughtered and transported to Umuahia, Abia state and Onitsha in Anambra State.³³ Igbo people also established another donkey slaughter camp where they conducted the trade in Maikwannugga Bush in Jangebe also in the present Zamfara State around 1973 – 1974. In Gulbinka Forest, Daki Takwas about 35,400 donkeys were slaughtered annually.³⁴ The Price of live donkey around 1976 in such place was between N 25 and N40 and the meat of one donkey was sold between N30 and N60.³⁵ Some igbo people that were involved in the trade include Mr. Chijoke, Mr. Ndukwe, Mr. Ndubisi, Mr World Bank, Maitumbi Joseph, Gajera Raphel e.t.c.

³² <http://www.ibtmes.com> Accessed 1/12015

³³ WJHCB/VET/SOK/63/2/17/Consumption of Donkey Meat

³⁴ WJHCB/VET/SOK/63/2/17/Consumption of Donkey Meat

³⁵ WJHCB/VET/SOK/63/2/17/Consumption of Donkey Meat

³⁶The discussion on donkey meat consumption and its impact on the trade in this paper centered particularly at Marrabah Idah (Tafa) in Kagoro Local Government Area of Kaduna State of Kaduna State and Ezamgbo in Ohaukwu Local Government of Ebonyi State. Donkey markets are particularly more prominent markets where Sokoto State donkey traders visited.

The status of donkeys had significantly changed from beasts of burden in some parts of northern Nigeria to source of protein in the southern Nigeria. The Igbo word for ‘donkey’ is derived from Hausa and was simply called ‘*jaki*’. This was adopted for nearly a century in donkey trade between north and south-east of the country transported in countless trailer loads.³⁷ In Ezamgbo in Ebonyi State, about 300 – 350 donkeys are slaughtered at the market’s abattoirs every day for human consumption. The market has thrived for over 80 years and served as the biggest donkey market in the whole of southern parts of Nigeria. Customers from other south eastern states also travel to the market to buy donkey meat.³⁸ An informant also confirmed that every day in the market about 300- 400 donkeys are slaughtered for sale to consumers. Some people sell fresh donkey meat while

³⁶ WJHCB/VET/SOK/63/2/17/Consumption

³⁷ <http://www.bcc.com>. Nigeria’s Ezamgbo Donkey Market Closes.

³⁸ <http://www.bcc.com>. Nigeria’s Ezamgbo Donkey Market Close. Accessed 10/4/2015

others sell roasted/fried donkey meat.³⁹ He added that during Christmas when the meat is in high demand, about 500-700 donkeys or more could be slaughtered every day.

Donkeys are brought from various places like Gaidam, Yobe State; Mai Adua Jibiya Dankama, Charanci, all in Katsina State; Babban Rame, Saho Rame, Illela, Achida, Sokoto, Shinkafi etc. There are about one thousand people who work in the market every day. The trade remained very important in providing jobs to many people.

On the other hand, however, farmers in different villages of northern Nigeria are complaining about the high rate of haulage of donkeys from the northern parts of the country to the southern states for consumption which resulted in the dwindling numbers of the animal. About 1,500 donkeys are transported to southern parts from Illela.⁴⁰ In Achida about 500-700 donkeys are sold and transported to other places. While about 200 donkeys are transported from Sokoto livestock market weekly to southern parts.⁴¹ The animals that are known as reliable means of transportation of farm produces are turned into delicacies on the dining table of some people.⁴²

³⁹ Alh. Abdullahi Oladipo, Oral interview.

⁴⁰ Interview with, Lawawaii sarkin shanu

⁴¹ Interview with Isah Bello, 50 years, Revenue collector of Sokoto Kara Market

⁴² Isah saidu

Most of the people who consume donkey meat are Igbo and some people from the northern parts of the country where donkeys are slaughtered. The processors and sellers of the meat are Igbo and other 'tribes' who are not Hausa.⁴³ Also, people of the South-south, south east and south west are the ones consume donkey meat and who visit Sokoto to buy donkeys. They process the meat and take it to Lagos or Ibandan for sale. Most people prefer donkey meat to any other meat that is why the trade is booming.⁴⁴ People prefer donkey meat than other meat because it is not costly. A person could buy it with little money ranging from N200.00 to N300.00.⁴⁵ Donkey becomes important to the extent that in Agbor in Delta State and Obollo Afo and Eha – Amufu, both in Enugu State, donkeys are used as special gift during funeral ceremonies of affluent persons.⁴⁶ Eluodin also stated that, the only issue which prevented Northerners do not consume donkey meat because of Islamic teaching coupled with abundant livestock the region is blessed with. Both old and young people consume the meat in the southern region. This enhanced the development of the trade to the extent that no matter how many numbers of

⁴³ Interview with Alh. Aminu Runji

⁴⁴ Interview with Alh. Aminu Runji The informant was one time used to convey donkeys to southern parts for sale to consumers.

⁴⁵ Interview with alh. Sani Na Isa

⁴⁶ V.A Yusuf et al, "Chinese are Going Gaga for Nigerian Donkeys" Daily trust Saturday, January 23,2016

donkey arrived in southern markets, they could be sold within a short time.⁴⁷

A respondent also stressed that consumers of donkey meat did not have any specific preferred species among the available donkey types in Sokoto State. The most preferred however, are the bigger ones. People who sell donkeys to consumers or those who sell the animal's skin could buy any types even if the animal is crippled or faced health challenge but on discounts. He also added that sick donkeys are no longer needed as all donkeys at the market must be physically seen.⁴⁸ According to veterinarian, donkey meat like any other livestock meat is a source of protein to human beings and the meat has no side effect in the human body.⁴⁹ It is a rich source of protein and contains the highest amount of protein when compared to mutton, pork, beef and chicken. Many people are comfortable with the consumption of donkey meat. Donkey meat had no health hazards like fattening since the animal's oil and fat does not solidify in the human body.⁵⁰

Some traders engaged in deceitful trade in some places.⁵¹ It was discovered in Mararraba Idah (near Abuja) in Kagoro Local Government area of Kaduna State

⁴⁷ Interview with Mathias Eluodin, 36 years, Donkey trader, Illela Market, 13/11/2016

⁴⁸ Interview with Irughe Nice day.....

⁴⁹ Interview with Chief Felix Avia,

⁵⁰ Interview with Alh. Kabiru Haliru Zoramawa.....

⁵¹ Interview with Musa Hassan

that some butchers developed the habit of slaughtering donkeys for sale in place of other types of meat to Abuja residence. This is an unethical practice. Some women also engage in buying dried donkey meat and sell them for cow meat.⁵²

5.0 Conclusion

Donkey trade developed to a certain level whereby its fate changed from being a non-profitable to a lucrative trade. This is largely because of the involvement of southerners who buy donkeys at high price for conveyance to southern parts of the country to sell to consumers. The development of the trade in donkey meat has recently changed the economic fate of the traders and resulted in the enrollment of large numbers of participants especially youths who found it easier as a way of materials gain. Prior to the emergence of southerners who buy and kill donkey for consumption the trade was neglected and regarded as local. However, with the involvement of southerners in the trade, the status of the trade uplifted to a national one and resulted in the rising of the animal prices to higher cost as well as becoming a lucrative business.

⁵² Adam umar Abuja, : Yadda Ake Cin naman jakuna A Abuja", jumu'a I, gaYuli, 2016